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Development and validation of a LC-MS/MS method for the simultaneous determination of aflatoxins, dyes and pesticides in spices.

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Abstract

Based on several alerts from European countries over the last years concerning spices we have been encouraged to establish an accurate method for the determination of dyes, aflatoxins and pesticides in various types of spices using reversed-phase (RP) liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry interfaced with electrospray (LC–ESI–MS/MS). A simple sample treatment procedure entailing the use of an extraction step with acetonitrile without further clean-up has been developed. A C18 column with an aqueous ammonium formate/methanol mixture as the mobile phase was used and gradient elution performed. Mass spectral acquisition was done in positive ion mode by applying multiple reaction monitoring of at least two fragmentation transitions per compound to provide the high degree of selectivity. The method was in-house validated in terms of linearity, sensitivity, repeatability, recovery, and selectivity on six kinds of spices. Satisfactory results in the majority of the cases were obtained for all analytes and matrices, with practical limits of quantitation acceptable for routine monitoring purposes.

Extraction recoveries for most of the compounds ranged from 60-140 % at spiking levels of 0.05 and 0.5 mg·kg⁻¹. The applicability of the method for the simultaneous determination of dyes, aflatoxins and pesticides in several types of spices was demonstrated and the method successfully applied to a limited number of products from the local market.

Keywords: LC-MS/MS, Food analysis, spices, pesticides, dyes, aflatoxins, validation study

Introduction

Spices have been used since antiquity as food additives for the purpose of colouring or flavouring and even for medication, and up to now they play an important role in the economy of the countries producing, importing or exporting them. However, over the past years they have also gained a further – although doubtful – importance as there were many alerts from European countries via the rapid alert system, indicating the need for expansion of the monitoring in this commodity. In most cases aflatoxins or azo-dyes were found in spices [1], especially in samples from developing countries (non-EU member states), furthermore there were also some reports of pesticides found in this type of commodity [2].

As food quality is an issue especially of aesthetical appeal it has been an age-old practice to use food colourants for increasing the pricing level of certain commodities; among them are certainly spices and other processed foods [3]. According to the literature azo-compounds are by far the most widely used synthetic colourants [4]. Azo-dyes are synthetic organic colourants, characterised by the common chromophoric azo groups ($N=N$). Next to Sudans I–IV, Para Red, Butter Yellow, Sudan Red and Sudan Orange G belong to the group of azo-dyes. Currently, there are over 3000 azo-dyes in use worldwide and they offer a wide spectrum of colours [5]. However, some of these organic colorants, especially the Sudan-dyes and their degradation products, have been recognized to be carcinogens [6] and therefore classified into category 3 by the International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC). Due to this known fact Sudan dyes are banned for use as food additives in the European Union (Sudan I according to the Decision 2003/460/EC [7]; Furthermore, the scope of measures has been expanded for Sudan II, III and IV in Decision 2004/92/EC [8]). Besides Sudan-dyes, also some other members of the azo-dyes are considered to have carcinogenic potential, which is why their presence has to be controlled due to their high risk for human health. The EU national authorities are responsible for ensuring the absence of Sudan-dyes in food products and to

ensure the EU legal requirements [8]. The usually proposed methods for the determination of these compounds are based on liquid chromatography (LC) with spectrophotometric UV [9] or fluorimetric [10] detection. Over the last few years electrospray (ESI) LC–mass spectrometry (MS) techniques [11] and especially LC-TOF/MS has been introduced to overcome problems associated with the high complexity of the spice samples, with the latter technique also allowing for the identification of isobaric ions known to occur in the analysis of these dyes [12].

A further prominent source of contamination in spices on top of the RASFF list are certainly aflatoxins. Aflatoxins (AFs) are considered unavoidable contaminants of food and feed, even under conditions of good manufacturing practices. According to estimations of the FAO more than 25 % of the world's agricultural production is contaminated with mycotoxins. Among the group of mycotoxins, aflatoxins (AF's B1, B2, G1 and G2 are naturally occurring) are the most often found ones and of major interest because they are classified as having genotoxic and carcinogenic effects [13]. Aflatoxin B1 is the most common one, usually comprising about 90% of the aflatoxin residue observed on contaminated foodstuffs. Aflatoxins are secondary metabolites of fungal species such as *Aspergillus flavus* or *Aspergillus parasiticus* growing on a variety of foods. In particular, peanuts, nuts, spices, and cereals are known to be often contaminated with this class of mycotoxins [14]. As mycotoxin contamination is favoured by particular climatic conditions, AFs occur mainly in hot and humid regions where high temperature and humidity are optimal for the growth of moulds and production of toxins [15]. Contamination of spices by aflatoxins and other mycotoxins may occur at any stage of production, from preharvest to drying and storage. The outstanding interest in aflatoxins is due to the fact that they are considered to be one of the most potent natural carcinogens. Due to their hepatotoxic and hepatocarcinogenic properties, the content of aflatoxins B1, B2, G1, and G2 in foods is restricted in many countries [16]. The European Union introduced measures to

minimise the presence of aflatoxins in different foodstuffs. Maximum residue levels (MRL) of aflatoxins (MRL for Aflatoxin B1: 5 µg/kg; sum of all aflatoxins: 10 µg/kg) are laid down in Commission Regulation (EC) No 1881/2006 [17]. Although products exceeding the maximum levels should not be placed on the market in the European Union (EU), an EU -wide screening during the years 2000–2006 revealed that these mycotoxins were still detectable in 26% of all analyzed foods [18], which points to the need for an effective food control. The most frequently used method to detect aflatoxins is HPLC coupled to fluorescence detection after extract cleanup by immunoaffinity chromatography (IAC) [19], but LC coupled to tandem mass spectrometry has gained increasing importance due to its superior specificity [20], [21], [22]. In recent years, the natural occurrence of aflatoxins in spices has been studied by several researchers [23-27].

Despite concerns regarding the contamination of spices with chemical dyes (e.g. Sudans and other azo-dyes) or mycotoxins, the situation regarding pesticide residues on this type of processed foods is unknown, as so far not too much comprehensive data are available. Although many papers deal with findings of pesticide residues in several matrices, only very few concern spices [28]. Spices are grown throughout the world; however, the most important exporting countries are mainly developing countries or third-world countries which may not comply with the legislative requirements of the European Community [29]. That's why it is absolutely important not only to look for conventionally used residues of pesticides, but also to include compounds already banned from the market, e.g. chlorinated hydrocarbons like DDT, as it has been shown that these hazardous compounds are still found in trace amounts [30]. Furthermore, spices are processed foodstuffs and may therefore contain lots of pesticide residues as a consequence of the application on the initial product, as is the case for example with several sorts of red pepper, chilli etc. Therefore, it is of importance to monitor them for the misuse or exceedance of certain pesticides, especially insecticides. So, even though it is very

likely to find numerous residues of pesticides in these processed foodstuffs it seems that there is no effective monitoring in this type of commodity in existence. One reason for this could be that spices are normally used only in very little amounts, so the overall dose might be considered neglectable. Another aspect is certainly the complex analytical challenge one has to cope with, involving more clean-up steps for residue analysis than in fruits or vegetables. Spices contain especially large amounts of essential oils and compounds of low polarity (monoterpenes and sesquiterpenes) and the more polar flavonoids [31, 32]. These compounds have molecular weights ranging from 130-400 Da. One possible way to get rid of the matrix interferences would be gel permeation chromatography or extensive sample clean-up, but such procedures increase the time and cost of the analysis, and clean-up generally leads to a loss in the number of pesticides that can be analyzed in the method (due to its inherent selectivity). Nowadays there is a strong tendency to introduce so-called multi-residue methods. One prominent example for such an approach is the Quechers method introduced previously [33], which has certainly given pesticide residue analysis an enormous boost. A further improvement along this line has been published recently, presenting a multi-component extraction method for the simultaneous determination of pesticides, mycotoxins, plant toxins and veterinary drugs in feed and food matrices [34].

Similarly, in this work we have developed and validated a LC-ESI-MS/MS method for the simultaneous identification and determination of the most important colouring dyes, aflatoxins and pesticides found and mentioned in various alerts in different types of spices. A careful validation procedure was followed to demonstrate data reliability and thus, that the analytical method presented here fits for its intended purpose. This includes in particular linearity, repeatability, recovery and selectivity. This simple and straightforward method described provides a significant advance in the multi-residue determination of spices and should be

suitable for the purpose of enforcement of the proposed EU MRLs, with the possibility to broaden the scope of compounds in this method.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents

The analytical standards of high purity (<98%) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Ausburg, Germany) and Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany). Individual stock solutions of all compounds ($1000 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$) were prepared in acetonitrile or methanol and stored at -20°C in the dark. A working standard solution containing all the compounds at a concentration of $5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ was prepared and stored at -20°C . This working standard solution was used to prepare the calibration curves, by dilution with either acetonitrile/water (50/50, v/v) or matrix extract/water (50/50, v/v).

HPLC-grade acetonitrile and methanol were obtained from VWR International (Leuven, Belgium). Ultra-pure HPLC-grade water was acquired from Promochem (Wessel, Germany). Ammonium formate was from Sigma Aldrich (Steinheim, Germany).

Sample preparation

Seven different kinds of spices were used for the development and validation of the method: curry powder, curcuma, chilli powder, paprika, ginger, nutmeg and black pepper. The selection criteria were based on the RASFF alerts over the last years, as well as on reported pesticide residues in the *Pesticides online* database [35]. Commercial samples were acquired in a local supermarket and were stored at room temperature until they were processed. A previous analysis of the samples was performed in order to ensure that they did not contain any of the studied compounds, and these samples were selected as blanks for spiking, calibration curves, and recovery purposes.

Spiking procedure

1 g of spice powder was weighed in a 15 ml disposable screw-capped polypropylene tube. Then, 0.1 ml of the standard mixture in acetonitrile of the desired concentration was carefully added, and it was left at room temperature for 15 minutes prior to extraction with the organic solvent. The final spiking concentration levels were of 0.05 and 0.5 mg·kg⁻¹ in the spices samples.

Extraction procedure

In order to achieve satisfactory results, different extraction conditions were assayed (type of extraction solvent, sample amount, and type of clean up). The following conditions were found to be optimal for the matrices tested.

A representative 1 g portion of solid sample (previously homogenized) was weighed into a 15 ml disposable screw-capped polypropylene tube, and 10 ml of acetonitrile were added. Then, the tube was shaken by hand for 30 seconds in order to allow the spices to mix thoroughly with the solvent, and the extraction continued for 30 minutes in an ultrasonic bath. Afterwards the tube was centrifuged at 3700 rpm for 4 minutes to sediment the solids. An aliquot (0.5 ml) of the extraction solution (containing 0.1 g sample·ml⁻¹) was diluted twofold with high-purity water, resulting in an extract containing 0.05 g sample·ml⁻¹. This final solution was filtered through a 0.2 µm PTFE (polytetrafluoroethylene) syringe filter (Whatman, Dassel, Germany) before injection into the LC-MS/MS.

LC-MS/MS Analysis

Liquid chromatography–electrospray ionization–tandem mass spectrometry, in positive ion mode, was used to separate, identify, and quantify the target compounds. For LC analysis, an

Agilent 1200 HPLC system with a binary pump and degasser was used. The analytical column employed was a reversed-phase C18 of 50mm×2mm and 4 μm particle size (Phenomenex Synergi Fusion-RP). The mobile phases A and B were ultrapure water/methanol (80/20, v/v, containing 5mM ammonium formate) and methanol/ultrapure water (90/10, v/v, containing 5mM ammonium formate), respectively. The gradient program started with 40% of B that increased linearly up to 100% in 10 minutes, and then remained constant for 15 minutes. After the 25 minutes run time, an equilibration step of 10 minutes at initial conditions was introduced. The flow rate was set constant at 0.2 ml·min⁻¹ during the whole process, with an autosampler temperature of 20°C and an injection volume of 10 μl.

A hybrid triple quadrupole linear ion trap (QqQLIT) 4000 QTRAPTM MS/MS analyzer (Applied Biosystem, Concord, Ontario, Canada) equipped with an electrospray source operating in positive ionization mode was used for detection in multiple reaction monitoring mode (MRM). Optimization of the compounds was performed by flow injection analysis (FIA), injecting individual standard solutions directly into the source. MRM experiments were carried out to obtain the maximum sensitivity for the detection of the target molecules. The main parameters were set as follows: Curtain Gas (CUR): 30 psi; Nebulizer Gas (GS1): 40 psi; Auxiliary Gas (GS2): 60 psi; Source Temperature: 550°C; Ion Spray Voltage (IS): 5000 V. Nitrogen was used as the nebulizer, curtain and collision gas. Table 1 shows the values of the instrumental settings optimized for each compound: declustering (DP) and entrance potential (EP) for precursor ions and collision energy (CE) for product ions. The best sensitivity in MRM operation mode was achieved through the acquisition of selected reaction monitoring (SRM) transitions at a dwell time of 30 ms for each mass transition (the total number of SRM transitions was 81 and the pause time 5 ms between scan cycles). Acquisition was performed in just one segment of the analysis, obtaining sufficient scans for each peak. For confirmation of the studied compounds two SRM transitions and a correct ratio between the abundances of the

two optimized SRM transitions (SRM2/SRM1) were used, along with retention time matching. In the case of the dyes, which are all banned in the European Union, three SRM transitions were optimized, in order to achieve further confirmation. For quantification, the most intense SRM transition was selected. Applied Biosystems/MDS SCIEX Analyst software 1.5 was used for data acquisition and processing

Validation Study

Method accuracy and precision was evaluated by recovery studies using blank matrices of the seven studied spices (curry powder, curcuma, chilli powder, paprika, ginger, nutmeg and black pepper) spiked at two concentration levels, 0.05 mg·kg⁻¹ and 0.5 mg·kg⁻¹. All experiments were tested with five replicates for each matrix, in accordance with EU guidelines [36]. Quantification of the compounds in the spiked samples was carried out comparing the peak areas of the samples with those of matrix matched standard solutions. These, as well as the matrix-matched calibration curves, were prepared by spiking an aliquot of the blank extract with the desired amount of standard solution. The sensitivity of the method was calculated in terms of practical limit of quantitation, or reporting level, which was calculated as the minimum concentration of analyte that generated a signal to noise ratio (S/N) of 3, determined in the confirmation transition (SRM2). Linearity was evaluated both in solvent and matrix, using matrix-matched calibration curves prepared as described before, in a concentration range of 0.001-0.1 mg·l⁻¹. The matrix effect was studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix. The repeatability of the instrumental method was estimated by determining the inter- and intra-day relative standard deviation (RSD, %) by the repeated analysis (n=5) of a spiked matrix extract at a 2.5 µg·kg⁻¹ and 25 µg·kg⁻¹ levels, from run-to-run over one day and five days, respectively.

Results and discussion

Optimization of LC-MS/MS parameters

Selection of the MS/MS conditions was performed individually for each analyte with direct infusion of $1 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ standard solution prepared in acetonitrile/water (50/50, v/v) at a flow rate of $0.005 \text{ ml}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. This process involved choosing the precursor and the product ions for each compound, as well as the optimum declustering and entrance potentials for the precursor ion and the collision energies for the product ions. These parameters are shown in Table 1. The transitions of the most abundant product ions (SRM1) were used for quantification and the second ones in abundance (SRM2), for confirmation. Due to the fact that the dyes included in this work are all banned in the European Union, and the known difficulties of their analysis, three SRM transitions were optimized, in order to achieve further confirmation. In most of the cases the base peak in the spectra corresponded to the protonated molecules $[\text{M}+\text{H}]^+$, except for rhodamin B $[\text{M}-\text{Cl}+\text{H}]^+$, orange II $[\text{M}-\text{Na}+\text{H}+\text{H}]^+$ and aldicarb $[\text{M}+\text{NH}_4]^+$. The product ions were selected to be as specific as possible, avoiding the use of common losses to prevent false positives in the analysis of such complex matrices. For spinosyn D only one product ion was obtained, as the fragmentation was difficult due to the stability of its macrocyclic structure. Figure 1 shows an extracted ion chromatogram (XIC) corresponding to 81 SRM transitions obtained at a concentration of $5 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ in curry extract. Figure 2 shows the SRM transitions of some representative compounds of each group investigated in a curry extract spiked with a standard solution mix at $5 \text{ }\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$.

Optimization of injection conditions

When dealing with so many different compounds in terms of chemical structures and properties the final conditions have to be a compromise solution in order to obtain the best results for most of them. The majority of the dyes and some of the pesticides studied show apolar

properties and hence elute later in the chromatographic method employed. On the other hand, aflatoxins, orange II and pesticides like acephate or omethoate elute very early. In the latter case the injection solvent plays an important role in the chromatographic method. If the proportion of organic solvent in the sample extract is higher than the initial chromatographic conditions, some peaks may split or show bad shape - mainly the more polar compounds. Therefore, injection should be performed in solvent conditions equal or equivalent to the initial mobile phase in order to avoid peak broadening and double peaks [37]. The extraction method developed provided a final extract in acetonitrile. As injection of the pure acetonitrile extract showed an adverse response to several compounds, the final extract was diluted with water (50/50, v/v), which gave good peak shapes for most of the compounds included in this work. Furthermore, best sensitivity could be achieved when injecting a volume of 10 µl per run.

Optimization of the extraction procedure

In a previous work, an extraction process for dyes in spices was developed [12]. This procedure was taken as the starting point for the simultaneous extraction of aflatoxins, dyes and pesticides. This method proved to be very effective, yielding very good recoveries for most of the compounds studied. However, the main drawback is the twentyfold dilution of the sample extract, leading to a lowered sensitivity, especially for aflatoxins. For optimization of the method, several different approaches were studied in order to reduce the dilution factor (extraction in water/acetonitrile 50/50, v/v; double the amount of material for extraction) or the matrix effect (clean-up with C18, PSA). Finally, due to the complex nature of the matrices, we ended up with the method described under extraction procedure in the *experimental section*, performing a high dilution of the matrix without any further clean-up step.

Method Validation

Validation was performed in accordance with EU Guidelines [36] of method validation procedures for pesticide residue analysis in food and feed (n=5, recovery between 70-120% and RSD lower than 20%), although several different criteria with respect to recovery and repeatability have been established in the different fields of determination of residues and contaminants. Performance characteristics studied were repeatability of the extraction method, linearity, matrix effects, specificity, and instrumental precision. Due to the large data set generated, the discussion part is limited to the noteworthy observations and overall results.

The precision of the method was verified by measuring recoveries from spiked blank samples of the different matrices investigated (curry powder, curcuma, chilli powder, paprika, ginger, nutmeg and black pepper) at two concentrations levels, 50 and 500 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. These fortification levels were selected according to the expected concentration for most of the compounds in real samples. These two levels also represent values at the lower and at the higher part of the linear range, as after the twentyfold dilution due to extraction, those concentrations would imply 2.5 and 25 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ in the extract. All experiments were performed with five replicates for each matrix. Mean recovery data and RSDs obtained, which express the repeatability of the extraction method are given in Table 2. For over 85 % of the compounds, recoveries were between 70-120% at high fortification level and roughly 80 % at low spiking level. According to the current EU guideline on quality control in pesticide residue analysis [36], the recoveries obtained during validation of the method should be within 70–120 %, but in certain justified cases, typically with multiresidue methods, recoveries outside this range may be accepted, especially if they are consistent. Due to the high complexity of the studied matrices, and considering the good repeatability of the method, we accepted those recoveries in the range 60–140 %, which is the range proposed by the guideline for routine analysis. All aflatoxins showed very good recoveries in the studied matrices, most of them with values from 100 % to 120 %.

Among the dyes, both Sudan IV and Sudan red 7B presented problems in most of the matrices. The lowest recoveries were those achieved for Sudan IV and Sudan red 7B.

Linearity was evaluated using solvent and matrix-matched calibration curves at five concentration levels, covering two orders of magnitude: from 0.001 – 0.1 mg·l⁻¹, based on linear regression and squared correlation coefficient (R²). Table 3 shows the R² of the matrix matched calibration curves. The linearity of the analytical response for all studied compounds within the range of two orders of magnitude was very good, with correlation coefficients higher than 0.996 in all cases.

Matrix effect was also evaluated during the validation of the method, as it is known that signal suppression or enhancement as a result of matrix effect can severely compromise quantitative analysis of the compounds at trace levels as well as method reproducibility [38]. The matrix effect was studied by comparison of the slopes of the calibration curves in solvent and in matrix. The percentage of the difference between these slopes is positive in case of signal enhancement, whereas a negative value is indicative for signal suppression. As illustrated in figure 3, most of the compounds showed signal suppression in the matrices investigated; only 4 % had soft or medium signal enhancement. The most critical matrix in terms of matrix effect was black pepper, where 67 % of the compounds showed strong signal suppression. In contrary, paprika presented the matrix with the lowest matrix effect. In view of these results we can confirm that these distributions depend not only on the matrix, but also on the combination of the compound and the matrix, so they are both compound-dependent and matrix-dependent. This fact highlights the importance of performing quantification with matrix matched calibration curves.

The specificity of the method was tested by analyzing blank samples. Due to the high complexity of the matrices, in some cases interfering peaks were present near or at the retention time of the target compounds in the SRM chromatograms when the selected transitions were

used. Therefore, a further confirmation step via the SRM ratio was used for the unambiguous confirmation of the present compounds. The recommended maximum permitted tolerances for relative ion intensities, calculated as the quotient between SRM2 and SRM1, are given in the SANCO analytical quality control procedures for pesticide residue analysis [36]. The tolerance range indicated in these guidelines for LC–MS techniques is from 20 % to 50 %. In order to validate this SRM ratio in matrix we calculated them for the standard solutions in solvent and in each matrix. Then we obtained the average value for a range of concentration from 1 to 100 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$. The confirmation criteria set for each compound were very stable all throughout the defined linearity range, with values of RSD < 20 %.

In order to evaluate the repeatability of the instrumental method, the intra- and inter-day RSD were studied. Method repeatability was determined at the two concentration levels of the recovery studies (including the twentyfold dilution), 2.5 and 25 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$, by analysis of five spiked matrix extracts (n=5) for each level and for each matrix tested. RSD for within matrix analysis ranged between 0.2 % and 9.7 %. This demonstrates the repeatability of the method and therefore its effectiveness for quantitative purposes.

The sensitivity of the method was calculated in terms of practical limit of quantitation or reporting level, which was calculated as the minimum concentration of analyte that generated a S/N of 3, determined in the confirmation transition (SRM2). The reporting levels of the studied compounds in the different matrices are shown in Table 4. They range from 0.2 to 10 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ for most analytes, which is usually sufficient to verify compliance of products with legal tolerances and to monitor the occurrence of undesirable substances in such complex food matrices.

Application to real samples

The proposed method was applied to the routine analysis of fifty spice samples purchased in different local markets in order to validate the suitability for routine analysis. The spices

belonged to the seven types of matrices in which the validation study was developed. The results showed that 55 % of the analyzed samples gave positive results (higher than the practical LOQ). For some of them, the MRLs established by the European legislation were even exceeded, which was the case for carbendazim, carbaryl and carbofuran. Traces of other compounds like dimethoate, imidacloprid or methamidophos were also detected. None of the studied samples presented aflatoxin contamination, but three of them contained Sudan I and another one Sudan IV. As an example, Figure 4 shows the specific SRM transitions of Sudan I in a real sample (spice mixture of paprika and curry powder), confirming the suitability of the developed method for monitoring of spices.

Conclusions

Using RP-LC under gradient conditions and ESI (+) detection mode, a reliable LC–MS/MS method for qualitative and quantitative analysis of dyes, aflatoxins and selected pesticides in various types of spices was developed. Selectivity of the MS/MS technique coupled with chromatographic separation proved to provide unambiguous identification and accurate determination of the compounds in complex matrices such as spices without the need of laborious clean-up procedures. Furthermore, the method has been validated for routine analysis using real market samples. Based on this work it will be possible to widen the scope of analytes to be measured according to the EU legal requirements.

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Fig. 1 Extracted ion chromatogram corresponding to the analysis of a curry extract spiked at 5 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ level with the studied compounds

Fig. 2 Selected SRM transitions of representative compounds for each group investigated in a curry extract spiked with a standard solution mix at $5 \mu\text{g}\cdot\text{l}^{-1}$ (a: Aflatoxin B1; b: Aflatoxin G1; c: Sudan I, d: Rhodamin B; e: Carbendazim; f: Methiocarb)

Fig. 3 Illustration of matrix effects in the different commodities used in this study. Signal enhancement (blue) and signal suppression categorized into weak (beige), high (orange) and strong (red)

Fig. 4 Extracted ion chromatogram of the three transitions corresponding to Sudan I in a real sample (spice mixture of paprika and curry powder)

Table 1. Values of the instrumental settings optimised for each compound: precursor ion, declustering potential (DP), entrance potential (EP), product ions and their collision energies (CE)

	Retention time (min)	Precursor ion (<i>m/z</i>)	DP (V)	EP (V)	Product ion 1 (<i>m/z</i>)	CE 1 (eV)	Product ion 2 (<i>m/z</i>)	CE 2 (eV)	Product ion 3 (<i>m/z</i>)	CE 3 (eV)
Aflatoxin B1	3.8	313.5	50	14	285.1	34	269	43	241.1	50
Aflatoxin B2	3.1	315	62	7	287.2	36	259.2	39	296.9	34
Aflatoxin G1	2.7	328.8	5	4	243.1	38	311.1	29	283	41
Aflatoxin G2	2.3	331.3	98	11	313.2	33	285.3	41	257.2	45
Sudan I	14.9	249.2	67	7	93.1	41	156	24	128	42
Sudan II	17.1	277.2	57	5	156	23	212.1	28	260.2	17
Sudan III	14.9 and 19.4	353.2	71	5	77.1	60	120.2	33	196.1	32
Sudan IV	16.5 and 24.4	381.2	87	5	90.9	48	224.1	32	106.1	57
Sudan orange G	10.9	215.3	50	6	93	33	121.9	24	198	21
Sudan red 7B	15.1 and 23.1	380.3	65	7	183	30	169	50	142	45
Sudan red G	14.8	279.2	58	6	123.1	29	108	51	248.1	17
Para red	14.4	294.1	65	7	156	27	127.9	42	248.3	29
Dimethyl yellow	13.4	226.8	50	6	77	34	121.1	38	94.9	28
Orange II	6.0	329	81	10	156	25	128	49	–	–
Rhodamine B	11.7	443.9	10	6	400.3	60	356.1	82	414.2	57
Acephate	1.2	184.12	31	10	142.9	13	112.9	33	–	–
Aldicarb	2.6	208.1	31	2	116	11	88.9	20	–	–
Amitraz	15.5	294.2	46	10	163.1	21	122	41	–	–
Carbaryl	4.6	202.1	51	10	145.1	16	127.1	39	–	–
Carbendazim	2.5	192	61	10	160	25	132	41	–	–
Carbofuran	3.7	222.1	50	10	165.2	17	123	29	–	–
Dimethoate	1.9	230	41	10	198.9	13	124.9	29	–	–
Epoxiconazole	11.3	330	56	10	121	27	101	63	–	–
Imazalil	12.4	297	46	10	159	31	201	23	–	–
Imidacloprid	1.5	256	71	10	209	21	175	25	–	–
Indoxacarb	13.5	528	96	10	203	51	56	55	–	–
Malathion	10.4	331.2	56	10	99	35	127.1	17	–	–
Methamidophos	0.9	142	51	10	94	19	125	17	–	–
Methiocarb	9.2	226.1	45	10	169.2	14	121	25	–	–
Methomyl	1.3	163.1	46	10	87.9	13	105.9	15	–	–
Omethoate	0.9	214	46	8	182.8	17	124.9	29	–	–
Pyridaben	15.8	365	41	10	147	31	309	19	–	–
Spinosyn A	15.1	732.4	66	10	142.2	41	98.2	93	–	–
Spinosyn D	5.7	746.5	81	10	142	53	–	–	–	–
Thiamethoxam	1.3	292	71	10	211	17	181	31	–	–
Triadimefon	10.4	294	56	10	197	21	225	19	–	–

Table 2. Recovery values and relative standard deviations (RSDs) of the target compounds in different spice matrices

Compound	Curry powder		Curcuma		Chilli powder		Ginger		Nutmeg		Paprika		Black pepper	
	R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a		R, % (RSD, %) ^a	
	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹	0.05 mg kg ⁻¹	0.5 mg kg ⁻¹
Aflatoxin B1	110 (3.1)	106 (1.1)	102 (9.1)	119 (1.9)	120 (4.0)	107 (3.3)	100 (8.1)	110 (2.7)	106 (2.3)	105 (2.2)	103 (4.9)	101 (4.7)	104 (4.6)	107 (3.7)
Aflatoxin B2	119 (4.9)	107 (0.6)	113 (2.6)	113 (1.8)	128 (5.2)	104 (3.8)	111 (3.2)	110 (3.0)	104 (5.8)	104 (3.4)	103 (2.4)	101 (1.3)	117 (1.2)	117 (1.6)
Aflatoxin G1	139 (1.5)	111 (1.5)	104 (7.4)	114 (2.3)	125 (3.3)	114 (3.2)	117 (3.3)	104 (3.8)	109 (4.5)	104 (3.1)	102 (5.2)	103 (3.3)	113 (7.3)	119 (2.7)
Aflatoxin G2	137 (3.7)	112 (2.0)	117 (2.3)	118 (1.9)	121 (6.6)	114 (2.1)	116 (5.6)	107 (3.3)	105 (3.8)	108 (3.5)	111 (6.2)	102 (3.1)	108 (9.7)	112 (2.5)
Sudan I	102 (5.8)	87 (3.8)	93 (14.8)	108 (3.8)	103 (6.7)	90 (5.0)	97 (3.1)	97 (3.9)	90 (5.9)	117 (6.9)	90 (8.3)	82 (4.4)	92 (12.9)	98 (3.9)
Sudan II	75 (4.2)	80 (2.2)	120 (7.6)	94 (1.7)	84 (9.1)	76 (3.9)	98 (7.0)	84 (2.3)	74 (6.0)	104 (11.6)	67 (3.2)	70 (3.2)	102 (4.9)	89 (2.8)
Sudan III	46 (12.4)	66 (7.8)	121 (4.2)	106 (0.9)	78 (16.7)	66 (7.5)	69 (1.4)	68 (4.8)	52 (4.8)	81 (3.9)	70 (16.3)	64 (7.9)	75 (9.7)	72 (1.2)
Sudan IV	29 (15.2)	53 (10.5)	129 (9.1)	99 (2.2)	70 (16.9)	57 (7.4)	47 (12.7)	48 (8.2)	42 (17.7)	67 (9.0)	51 (20.2)	52 (12.0)	52 (9.1)	52 (2.8)
Sudan orange G	99 (10.8)	116 (3.2)	100 (3.2)	107 (1.7)	108 (5.1)	112 (2.5)	105 (4.7)	102 (2.9)	104 (7.3)	113 (4.8)	102 (3.2)	113 (1.6)	96 (4.0)	55 (15.4)
Sudan red 7B	19 (5.1)	53 (13.1)	159 (8.2)	96 (1.2)	73 (4.4)	59 (6.1)	36 (3.6)	37 (7.4)	33 (7.0)	68 (3.7)	57 (11.6)	59 (7.6)	70 (14.5)	46 (17.6)
Sudan red G	107 (1.7)	93 (3.2)	108 (2.7)	108 (0.7)	104 (5.6)	97 (4.0)	99 (3.9)	98 (4.4)	101 (6.6)	136 (12.7)	89 (1.9)	86 (4.6)	95 (8.3)	102 (2.9)
Para red	101 (2.0)	89 (3.7)	115 (6.1)	114 (2.7)	104 (6.5)	95 (3.7)	108 (6.7)	98 (2.5)	95 (7.8)	118 (8.1)	96 (3.1)	87 (4.2)	95 (9.2)	106 (2.7)
Dimethyl yellow	104 (14.7)	93 (3.3)	118 (15.2)	124 (7.4)	109 (8.5)	107 (7.3)	130 (7.7)	102 (2.4)	155 (26.9)	117 (12.7)	100 (8.3)	85 (4.3)	106 (7.3)	117 (10.4)
Orange II	93 (5.9)	87 (6.7)	103 (7.7)	91 (3.3)	108 (5.2)	104 (2.4)	109 (5.2)	107 (3.9)	97 (8.8)	72 (4.8)	84 (10.9)	96 (4.9)	< LOQ	101 (2.6)
Rhodamine B	105 (6.0)	97 (3.0)	114 (8.5)	102 (6.6)	107 (4.2)	98 (1.6)	103 (2.4)	101 (2.3)	36 (14.3)	35 (11.3)	115 (6.7)	94 (2.5)	113 (6.5)	104 (3.2)
Acephate	169 (8.5)	120 (9.4)	86 (12.9)	167 (6.3)	140 (7.9)	150 (8.4)	99 (9.8)	98 (7.7)	92 (4.6)	89 (3.5)	100 (4.9)	78 (10.1)	101 (6.9)	89 (5.7)
Aldicarb	129 (6.2)	106 (4.1)	118 (11.5)	100 (13.9)	117 (10.0)	97 (4.1)	101 (9.7)	120 (9.7)	102 (3.8)	108 (4.3)	121 (1.6)	99 (11.2)	118 (13.4)	123 (5.3)
Amitraz	129 (7.5)	78 (6.4)	114 (1.9)	105 (2.1)	102 (3.1)	83 (3.8)	99 (3.6)	95 (2.7)	79 (4.0)	118 (6.4)	189 (15.4)	44 (11.9)	98 (2.5)	105 (0.4)
Carbaryl	120 (3.2)	117 (1.3)	123 (3.5)	111 (1.5)	116 (1.4)	120 (0.7)	107 (2.4)	113 (2.4)	115 (4.6)	110 (3.2)	106 (2.5)	110 (3.7)	114 (3.0)	120 (3.5)
Carbendazim	119 (2.6)	105 (1.2)	121 (1.2)	107 (1.9)	92 (0.8)	105 (0.9)	103 (9.4)	107 (2.5)	99 (2.6)	100 (3.4)	97 (3.3)	94 (3.0)	112 (3.9)	108 (3.0)
Carbofuran	129 (2.4)	108 (1.1)	120 (2.5)	111 (1.0)	107 (1.1)	109 (0.6)	108 (3.2)	111 (3.0)	113 (3.9)	104 (2.3)	105 (1.5)	102 (2.2)	116 (1.6)	115 (1.4)
Dimethoate	152 (0.8)	108 (1.5)	119 (2.7)	117 (2.8)	142 (1.9)	114 (3.0)	118 (4.3)	111 (3.0)	110 (3.5)	103 (2.3)	113 (1.9)	98 (2.5)	120 (0.9)	113 (2.6)
Epoxiconazole	101 (4.0)	102 (0.9)	120 (6.9)	111 (4.0)	109 (2.2)	104 (2.1)	101 (2.1)	106 (1.9)	101 (2.2)	119 (6.1)	107 (6.9)	97 (3.2)	105 (6.3)	104 (1.8)
Imazalil	125 (2.5)	103 (2.3)	113 (4.5)	106 (1.2)	104 (6.4)	103 (2.0)	92 (7.7)	99 (2.0)	97 (5.3)	90 (6.2)	98 (3.4)	93 (2.2)	126 (9.5)	114 (4.5)
Imidacloprid	182 (4.5)	108 (4.5)	130 (4.1)	142 (2.2)	101 (2.3)	124 (7.2)	111 (6.4)	110 (4.6)	106 (8.5)	98 (2.5)	111 (3.7)	97 (6.2)	118 (6.1)	112 (5.0)
Indoxacarb	103 (12.1)	101 (3.6)	120 (3.6)	109 (5.9)	109 (16.0)	88 (5.4)	109 (15.6)	101 (4.1)	135 (7.0)	126 (9.7)	99 (5.8)	95 (4.1)	98 (10.1)	104 (5.2)
Malathion	135 (4.9)	107 (2.0)	121 (1.7)	103 (0.5)	101 (12.6)	106 (3.8)	107 (1.9)	105 (4.8)	98 (5.0)	129 (4.0)	101 (2.2)	100 (2.2)	101 (4.0)	114 (6.2)
Methamidophos	128 (6.8)	109 (9.6)	105 (15.8)	159 (3.8)	154 (10.1)	152 (7.8)	101 (6.0)	94 (8.3)	84 (7.1)	85 (4.0)	111 (1.5)	82 (10.7)	98 (5.7)	87 (4.8)

Methiocarb	140 (2.4)	117 (2.3)	128 (3.2)	112 (0.2)	113 (2.2)	119 (2.0)	112 (6.5)	111 (2.4)	105 (5.2)	136 (8.9)	98 (2.0)	106 (2.0)	111 (5.2)	118 (1.0)
Methomyl	190 (4.2)	105 (7.9)	118 (4.4)	142 (3.9)	135 (5.1)	145 (9.8)	144 (8.2)	129 (4.8)	86 (6.2)	109 (1.1)	119 (4.6)	88 (6.1)	102 (6.0)	113 (3.5)
Omethoate	202 (7.6)	115 (9.3)	105 (13.9)	161 (3.9)	198 (6.5)	167 (14.9)	107 (7.5)	101 (6.6)	89 (4.7)	92 (3.2)	119 (7.3)	83 (7.6)	99 (3.8)	89 (4.4)
Pyridaben	97 (4.4)	92 (3.0)	115 (2.8)	115 (4.4)	100 (4.4)	90 (3.2)	102 (2.0)	96 (3.9)	102 (5.0)	133 (11.3)	83 (2.8)	86 (4.1)	96 (4.1)	100 (2.9)
Spinosyn A	109 (5.0)	104 (1.7)	94 (16.0)	106 (4.5)	103 (3.6)	102 (1.8)	104 (5.2)	99 (3.5)	85 (5.3)	81 (6.7)	102 (4.6)	99 (1.9)	105 (4.5)	105 (1.9)
Spinosyn D	119 (8.8)	101 (1.9)	101 (6.0)	119 (4.4)	101 (4.4)	99 (2.8)	96 (6.6)	101 (5.3)	75 (4.6)	71 (5.7)	113 (5.0)	97 (3.3)	94 (4.8)	104 (1.8)
Thiamethoxam	241 (5.2)	114 (9.0)	125 (3.5)	163 (3.2)	201 (4.5)	149 (11.7)	119 (11.3)	116 (10.1)	86 (8.2)	92 (4.1)	113 (6.6)	91 (7.1)	100 (8.9)	98 (6.3)
Triadimefon	119 (3.3)	108 (3.3)	102 (9.0)	111 (2.2)	119 (4.5)	108 (1.8)	106 (5.1)	102 (5.0)	115 (11.5)	132 (11.4)	102 (4.1)	102 (2.5)	102 (8.2)	106 (3.3)

Spiking levels 0.05 and 0.5 mg kg⁻¹

^a Mean recovery and relative standard deviation from analysis of spiked samples (n=5)

Table 3. Matrix effect of the different spice matrices

Compound	Matrix effect (%) ^a						
	Curry powder	Curcuma	Chilli powder	Ginger	Nutmeg	Paprika	Black pepper
Aflatoxin B1	-9.7	-40.7	-5.6	-32.0	-7.3	-4.4	-28.2
Aflatoxin B2	-19.9	-31.5	-13.2	-30.6	-19.4	-16.2	-54.3
Aflatoxin G1	-22.6	-37.0	-18.7	-21.0	-16.4	-10.6	-56.4
Aflatoxin G2	-23.1	-30.4	-17.3	-30.8	-23.9	-20.1	-42.1
Sudan I	-37.7	-62.9	-34.8	-53.9	-47.8	-27.0	-75.2
Sudan II	-37.3	-52.1	-29.3	-67.2	-62.7	-37.3	-72.2
Sudan III	-13.3	-34.7	2.5	-54.4	-49.2	-20.9	-65.1
Sudan IV	-12.9	-13.4	0.2	-34.8	-45.3	-32.0	-21.8
Sudan orange G	-50.7	-61.9	-33.5	-38.7	-59.2	-8.8	-98.3
Sudan red 7B	-27.7	-37.3	-16.7	-36.6	-34.9	-37.1	-79.5
Sudan red G	-37.3	-66.1	-30.0	-64.1	-74.5	-32.4	-76.4
Para red	-30.8	-69.1	-15.2	-49.0	-64.9	-10.4	-79.3
Dimethyl yellow	-53.3	-49.8	-19.8	-54.1	-61.7	-8.9	-70.6
Orange II	6.1	19.5	-1.7	20.6	33.6	12.1	27.2
Rhodamine B	-7.1	-16.9	-10.2	4.7	-29.7	-9.1	-25.6
Acephate	-62.4	-64.0	-70.6	-63.3	-50.9	-75.0	-64.4
Aldicarb	-36.6	-42.8	-29.8	-23.6	-15.8	-26.4	-56.5
Amitraz	-80.3	-30.7	-43.1	-44.0	-76.1	-97.0	-49.4
Carbaryl	-69.2	-77.1	-68.2	-10.9	-15.0	-4.6	-36.1
Carbendazim	-28.8	-38.5	-28.1	-31.2	-23.0	-16.4	-41.2
Carbofuran	-17.1	-43.6	-15.1	-29.8	-9.7	-4.4	-20.4
Dimethoate	-25.6	-27.4	-29.2	-22.9	-13.6	-23.1	-33.1
Epoxiconazole	-25.8	-89.4	-12.6	-39.1	-52.4	-13.1	-66.7
Imazalil	-37.4	-29.5	-22.0	-31.4	-13.8	-59.5	-84.6
Imidacloprid	-28.8	-47.9	-41.0	-44.4	-21.3	-47.0	-54.5
Indoxacarb	-9.5	-27.4	-3.3	-22.3	-37.7	6.4	-65.2
Malathion	-43.5	-67.5	-36.4	-35.7	-85.8	-3.6	-86.7
Methamidophos	-67.5	-68.3	-74.2	-61.8	-51.0	-74.0	-61.7
Methiocarb	-66.9	-68.8	-16.7	-88.6	-61.0	-2.4	-76.5
Methomyl	-55.3	-54.6	-67.7	-49.8	-35.9	-69.0	-62.7
Omethoate	-63.9	-64.7	-71.4	-61.2	-51.0	-74.1	-60.9
Pyridaben	-34.0	-35.2	-22.5	-33.2	-31.4	-16.3	-78.5
Spinosyn A	-31.4	-37.4	-20.6	-29.1	-46.0	9.0	-36.0
Spinosyn D	-33.1	-33.0	-30.4	-30.6	-47.6	-6.9	-34.0
Thiamethoxam	-53.9	-71.7	-62.8	-59.6	-42.1	-68.1	-68.9
Triadimefon	-42.6	-70.1	-41.1	-24.3	-86.9	-5.6	-79.2

Table 4. Reporting levels (practical limit of quantification) of the studied compounds in the different matrices

	Practical Limits of quantitation ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)						
	Curry powder	Curcuma	Chilli powder	Ginger	Nutmeg	Paprika	Black pepper
Aflatoxin B1	1.7	3.9	1.0	2.6	2.4	2.7	3.0
Aflatoxin B2	2.2	2.7	2.1	3.5	1.0	2.5	3.3
Aflatoxin G1	8.3	8.7	13.6	7.5	9.7	9.1	20.0
Aflatoxin G2	10.0	5.9	3.6	6.1	4.1	5.9	6.3
Sudan I	1.5	4.4	1.2	2.6	1.5	1.7	2.8
Sudan II	1.5	1.6	1.1	3.6	2.6	1.9	3.2
Sudan III	4.0	5.2	1.8	5.8	3.2	1.8	2.7
Sudan IV	2.0	2.8	2.5	3.1	3.5	4.1	3.3
Sudan orange G	2.2	8.0	1.4	3.4	3.2	2.2	9.2
Sudan red 7B	2.0	1.8	1.3	1.8	1.6	1.2	2.0
Sudan red G	0.7	1.2	1.7	3.4	2.9	0.5	2.2
Para red	2.2	4.0	1.0	3.6	1.3	1.2	7.1
Dimethyl yellow	55.6	100.0	83.3	100.0	100.0	35.7	265.5
Orange II	47.6	21.7	46.2	6.6	53.6	29.4	61.2
Rhodamine B	1.3	0.8	1.1	0.7	1.3	1.7	0.9
Acephate	20.0	12.5	9.0	2.1	5.0	10.3	7.1
Aldicarb	5.9	4.9	2.4	4.3	5.5	5.5	8.5
Amitraz	5.1	1.2	2.0	8.5	1.2	3.0	1.2
Carbaryl	1.2	1.1	0.9	1.3	1.0	0.8	1.9
Carbendazim	4.9	4.7	0.4	4.0	4.3	20.0	3.7
Carbofuran	1.0	1.4	0.7	1.8	0.7	1.0	1.0
Dimethoate	2.2	1.2	1.8	1.8	1.5	2.5	1.1
Epoxiconazole	0.7	4.1	0.7	1.7	1.0	0.7	3.8
Imazalil	4.1	3.7	3.8	5.6	3.0	3.5	7.5
Imidacloprid	3.5	5.0	1.0	3.8	2.1	7.2	4.2
Indoxacarb	8.2	11.8	2.2	10.0	15.8	0.5	42.5
Malathion	0.5	0.5	0.7	0.7	1.7	0.2	3.3
Methamidophos	20.0	11.1	12.2	10.7	9.5	6.2	9.7
Methiocarb	2.0	1.1	0.4	16.2	1.1	0.6	4.1
Methomyl	18.2	11.8	11.3	5.6	5.1	20.0	9.7
Omethoate	2.5	0.6	1.8	1.0	1.3	3.0	1.4
Pyridaben	0.8	1.4	0.4	0.8	0.9	0.4	1.2
Spinosyn A	2.6	1.6	1.1	1.4	5.6	0.5	6.4
Spinosyn D	1.4	3.4	1.1	2.9	1.8	2.4	2.1
Thiamethoxam	9.7	15.5	15.4	3.1	2.2	10.4	8.8
Triadimefon	1.7	0.8	2.6	1.6	3.1	0.5	2.8

Table 5. Incidence and range of contaminants found in various spice samples purchased from the local stores

Matrix (no. of samples)	Contaminants	Number of samples	Range of concentration ($\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$)	Number of samples above MRL ^{a,b}
Paprika (16)	Carbendazim	10	25.0–386.1	4 ^b
	Carbaryl	2	7.3–500.7	1 ^b
	Carbofuran	7	1.4–31.0	–
	Dimethoate	2	3.0–3.2	–
	Imidacloprid	1	12.5	–
	Indoxacarb	2	5.5–13.0	–
	Methamidophos	1	33.5	–
	Methomyl	1	23.4	–
	Spinosad	2	2.0–2.1	–
	None	4	–	–
Spice mixes and others (9)	Sudan I	3	57.0-780.7	3 ^a
	Sudan IV	1	28.5	1 ^a
	Carbendazim	4	11.0-222.7	1 ^b
	Carbaryl	2	2.2–9.7	–
	Carbofuran	3	1.1–13.8	–
	Imidacloprid	1	24.0	–
	Methomyl	1	21.0	–
	Spinosad	1	2.5	–
	None	4	–	–
	Curry (7)	Carbendazim	4	5.0–89.9
Carbofuran		2	12.0–15.5	–
None		2	–	–
Pepper (black and white) (5)	Carbendazim	3	8.1–17.3	–
	None	2	–	–
Chilli (4)	Carbendazim	2	1.3–4.4	–
	Carbofuran	2	3.0–3.7	–
	None	2	–	–
Curcuma (3)	Carbendazim	1	9.2	–
	None	2	–	–
Nutmeg (3)	None	3	–	–
Ginger (3)	None	3	–	–

^a According to Commission Regulation (EC) No. 1881/2006

^b According to Regulation (EC) No. 396/2005